

GENYO DAY IMPLEMENTATION IN THE BASIC EDUCATION SCHOOL: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY

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Genyo Day Implementation in the Basic Education School: an Exploratory Study

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Abstract

This qualitative study examined the opinions, experiences, and concerns expressed by students and teachers regarding the implementation of "Genyo Day" at the University of Saint Louis (USL) during the 2023–2024 academic year. The data were collected from twenty-one Basic Education School teachers and twenty-three learners, in accordance with Merriam and Tisdell's (2016) fundamental qualitative research methodologies. Thematic analysis revealed both advantages and challenges when examining the primary themes of "Genyo Day." The results indicated that "Genyo Day" provides participants with enhanced learning and preparation time, academic flexibility, the opportunity for relaxation and personalization, and a greater understanding of themselves. However, it also introduces concerns regarding technical and connectivity issues, misuse, and productivity. This research provides novel perspectives on the outcomes of "Genyo Day" and suggests additional improvements to increase its significance in educational settings.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Productivity, Generation Z, Academic Flexibility

INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions worldwide are embracing digital platforms to enhance student engagement, personalize learning experiences, and prepare learners for the challenges of the 21st century. One such innovative approach is the integration of e-learning, such as learning management systems, in the educational system. Learning management systems (LMS) are platforms that assist in the delivery of content online for learning purposes. It enables organizations and educational institutions to manage and deliver online courses and programs, providing an interactive and engaging learning experience for users (Amutha & Prasath, 2023). It had a positive effect on learners' critical thinking, regulation, learning ability, and academic achievement (Huang & Sun, 2022).

Various private schools in the Philippines use Genyo E-learning as one of their learning management systems. In the study of Capacio (2021), Genyo e-learning improves achievement in students compared to conventional virtual lecture method teaching. Another study by Baraquia (2021) asserted that the implementation of Genyo e-learning successful and effective. The Basic Education School of the University of Saint Louis utilizes Genyo as the learning management system in the school year 2023-2024. In light of this, the Basic Education School of the University of Saint Louis has implemented 'Genyo Day' as a strategic initiative. This initiative aims to designate a specific day, usually Wednesdays, when students and teachers can engage with Genyo e-learning. Genyo is a

fully integrated e-learning platform with rich curriculum-based content, a responsive support system, and a dynamic implementation program. With the use of Genyo, teachers improved their instruction and students improved their study habits (Ferrer & Celario, 2019).

While numerous studies have examined the benefits of learning management systems (LMS) like Genyo e-learning in improving student engagement, critical thinking, and achievement (Capacio, 2021; Baraquia, 2021; Ferrer & Celario, 2019), there is a substantial gap in the understanding of the impact of the structured integration of LMS, such as the "Genyo Day" initiative, on broader educational outcomes. In particular, there is a dearth of research that examines the direct effects of a dedicated LMS engagement day on student performance, engagement levels, and long-term retention in academic subjects within a basic education context. Additionally, although the majority of research focuses on the general benefits of learning management systems (LMS), it fails to offer a thorough analysis of the mechanisms by which specific LMS activities and content utilization patterns (e.g., multimedia resources, interactive lessons) influence individual learning preferences and outcomes. Addressing this disparity would provide valuable insights into the optimization of digital learning schedules and resources to improve academic performance and personalize learning.

By utilizing Genyo e-learning on 'Genyo Day', schools aim to optimize instructional time, cater to individual learning preferences, and foster a deeper understanding of academic subjects beyond the confines

of traditional classroom settings. This platform offers a diverse array of digital resources, including interactive lessons, multimedia content, assessments, and collaborative tools aimed at reinforcing classroom instruction and promoting self-directed learning (Sobejana, 2020). This study seeks to explore the implementation of 'Genyo Day' in basic education schools, examining its impact on student engagement, academic performance, and overall educational effectiveness.

Research Objectives

This study aims to explore the experiences of teachers and students regarding the implementation of 'Genyo Day', with a focus on identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement in its educational outcomes and operational effectiveness.

Research Assumption

Both teachers and students perceive 'Genyo Day' as a beneficial initiative that enhances learning experiences through increased access to interactive digital resources, thereby promoting engagement and potentially improving academic outcomes. The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide insights into the implementation of 'Genyo Day' in the Basic Education School, a strategy for integrating digital learning platforms into traditional educational settings. By examining the experiences of teachers and students, the study contributes valuable knowledge on the effectiveness of 'Genyo Day' in enhancing educational practices. Understanding the strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement of 'Genyo Day' can inform educational policymakers, school administrators, and educators about best practices for leveraging technology to enrich learning environments. Ultimately, the findings of this study can facilitate informed decision-making and the development of strategies to optimize educational outcomes and foster holistic student development in today's digital age.

Literature Review

Turnbull et al. (2020) say that Learning Management Systems (LMS) must be used regularly and are now an important part of education. Alqahtani and Rajkhan (2020) say that LMSs need management and technical help to work well in times of fast change. Nguyen (2021), on the other hand, says that users need to be happy with LMSs so they keep using them. To reach this level of happiness, the technology must be effective, simple, and able to meet the wants and goals

of the customer. Turnbull, Chugh, and Luck (2023) say that adding social media to LMS systems could make classrooms more interactive and social. According to Díaz Redondo et al. (2021), adding micro-learning tools to LMS systems makes students more interested and helps them learn more. As the need for classes that are flexible and can fit a wide range of kids grows, this mix helps meet that need.

Ashrafi et al. (2022) also say that how students see the value of LMS features in helping them do well in school, how well the system works, and how easy it is to use are all big factors in how much they use LMS systems. Their wide range of methods really shows how hard it is to make the link between system design, administrative support, and student standards. Lopes et al. (2022) say that quality control is very important for making sure that new digital technologies are put together properly. Making people learn through LMSs has also changed how people are taught in a big way. In 2020, Mpungose says that the shift to online learning has an impact on South African schools. He believes that variations in digital skills and access to stable internet may be the main reason why it's hard for people to use LMS. Learning management systems (LMS) can make education more adaptable and scalable, but they need to be properly connected to other digital tools, tailored to the needs of their users, and backed by strong support from the school. If schools want LMS to keep growing in the education field, they need to fix problems with how it works, how it is managed, and how it is taught. They also need to set up places where students and teachers can use digital tools for learning (Vasiliev et al., 2021).

There is a big difference between how well kids do in school, how interested they are in learning, and how involved their parents are. In 2022, Cariaga shows that LMS systems with flexible lesson plans helped keep math classes going while the pandemic was going on. Teachers can use these sites to send and receive tools and notes from far away. Cariaga (2024) says that the 21st century's educational goals should be to help students think critically, communicate effectively, work together, and be creative. These parts of the LMS get students interested and help them do well in school by making them learn on their own. Another important thing for parents to do is help their kids learn to read and do math. LMS can make this simple. LMS tools that let parents see kid's growth in real time let parents keep an eye on them as they learn. Now, families and schools can work together better, which is especially helpful in distant areas without many resources. Family support grows when you do things like this, and that support is linked to doing better

in school (Cariaga, Pospos, & Dagunan, 2024). Plus, they say that LMS sites let parents and teachers talk to each other, which makes the network of people who can help kids better.

Learner-designed studies are one creative way that LMS platforms make science more open and interesting for all students because they let them learn at their own pace (Estrella, 2024; Harriet et al., 2024). In 2023, Amutha and Prasath said that interesting tools like those on Genyo e-learning give students lessonbased material that they can learn on their own and that helps them learn skills like problem-solving and critical thinking. Ginoo, Maique, and Inoc (2023) say that these tools let students learn outside of school and give them chances to learn more, get stronger, and be more versatile. LMS tools definitely help kids do better in school and keep them inspired in many school settings. The University of Saint Louis Basic Education School's "Genyo Day" program uses digital tools to make the most of class time, teach students how to use the LMS, and tailor their learning (Ferrer & Celario, 2019). Students can learn simple skills at their own pace when they have time to use an LMS. For kids who need extra help in school, this is very helpful. It is clear that using an LMS platform can help, but more study is needed to fully understand how they affect drive, skill memory, and long-term grade success. Cariaga et al. (2024) and Cariaga & Dagunan (2023) say that there needs to be more research on how LMS can help students get better at reading and math. This will help schools help students and teachers more. While schools look at and improve programs like "Genyo Day," they can help students form long-lasting digital learning habits that will help them get ready for the global job market and adjust to the changes in education.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative type of research employing the basic qualitative research by Merriam & Tisdell (2016). The study included 21 BES teachers and 23 BES students from USL during the school year 2023-2024 as respondents. We utilized a survey question through Google Form as the primary data collection tool. We gathered data about positive experiences, issues and challenges, and areas of improvement using a Google Form. We utilized thematic analysis to explore the experiences of teachers and students regarding the implementation of the Genyo day in the Basic Education School, with the aim of identifying strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theme 1: Positive Experiences of Teachers and Students in Genyo Day

Genyo Day has emerged as a cornerstone of positive experiences for both teachers and students alike, offering a blend of flexibility, productivity, and personalization within the educational landscape. For teachers, it represents an opportunity to streamline administrative tasks, enhance lesson planning, and engage in professional development activities. This dedicated time allows educators to catch up on grading, curriculum development, and classroom preparations, ensuring that instructional quality remains high. Simultaneously, students benefit immensely from Genyo Day by gaining additional study time, accessing resources for advanced learning, and enjoying moments of rest and rejuvenation crucial for their overall well-being. The platform's versatility facilitates seamless communication, collaborative learning experiences, and tailored academic support, making Genyo Day a cornerstone of educational success and satisfaction for both teachers and students.

1. 1. Academic Flexibility and Productivity

Genyo Day has transformed how students and teachers approach learning and teaching, offering flexibility and productivity. For students, it's a dedicated time to dig deeper into their studies without the usual pressures of a regular school day. They can review lessons, prepare for upcoming assessments, and manage their academic workload at their own Teachers utilize Genyo Day to streamline administrative tasks and enhance lesson planning. Through video lectures and shared resources like PowerPoint presentations, instructors ensure that learning continues seamlessly, even when face-to-face teaching time is limited.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO1: "More time for studying without the feeling for overwhelmed."

SO2: "Genyo Day allows me to review my lessons for upcoming quizzes and do other academic tasks at home."

SO3: "It's a great way to catch up on tasks, especially during 'hell week'."

TO5: "Teachers use Genyo Day to catch up with backlogs like checking, DLP writing, and more."

TO7: "Genyo provides a more relaxed and flexible learning environment, fostering greater time management."

Flexible time allows teachers and students to better manage their work-life balance, which can lead to reduced stress and burnout. With greater control over their schedules, teachers can attend to family needs without using up all their leave, adjust their hours to align with students' needs, and pursue hobbies and interests that recharge them (Ahmadi et.al, 2024). This improved work-life balance ultimately allows teachers to be more focused and effective in the classroom (Editor, 2021). This means that teachers with flexible time can be productive and will lead to effective teaching. Another study by Soffer (2020) shows that students developed different patterns of learning time, place, and access to content, which indicates that flexibility was used substantially. This implies that flexibility affects the productivity of students, thus, lead to better academic performance.

1.2. Opportunities for Rest and Personalization

Beyond its academic benefits, Genyo Day serves as a period for students and teachers to rejuvenate and personalize their learning experience. It offers a much-needed break from the rigors of regular classes, allowing students to rest, recharge, and manage their time effectively. Whether it's catching up on group projects or simply taking a breather, students appreciate the freedom to prioritize tasks according to their needs. Similarly, teachers find Genyo Day invaluable for attending to personal tasks and professional development, promoting a balanced approach to their teaching responsibilities. This subtheme underscores how Genyo Day supports holistic student well-being and enhances teaching efficacy through personalized learning opportunities.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO2: "It's also a time for all students to have some rest."

S11: "I appreciate the freedom to handle my time, either to rest or finish group works."

SO4: "Genyo Day serves as a rest day for students, which is beneficial for overall health."

SO9: "A break from early mornings, and ample time to finish any weekly tasks."

TO7: "It ultimately allows us to create and enjoy a schedule that best fits with our day-to-day activities."

T11: "Teachers use Genyo Day to prepare lesson plans, which results to more planned and executed lessons."

T16: "It promoted better work-life balance and wellbeing, minimizing the need to take home paperwork."

Learning is a personalized experience that allows one to expand their knowledge, perspective, skills, and understanding. Therefore, personalized learning can help to meet individual needs and goals. Furthermore, to personalize the learning experience, technology integration can play a crucial role (Shemshack & Spector, 2020). With the integration of learning management system such as Genyo, students and teachers can personalize their learning experience and at the same time may promote their well-being.

Furthermore, wellbeing in teachers and students can be improved through reducing emotional exhaustion, improving working conditions, and fostering intrinsic motivation (Putwain, 2019). This suggests that with the implementation of Genyo day, teachers and students may enhance their well-being.

1.3. Enhanced Learning and Preparation

Genyo Day enhanced learning and thorough preparation among students and teachers alike. It plays a role in bridging gaps caused by missed classes due to various school events, ensuring continuity in education. Students capitalize on this time to catch up on assignments, quizzes, and academic tasks, fostering a proactive approach to their studies. Meanwhile, teachers utilize Genyo's flexible platform to upload supplementary materials, facilitate collaborative learning activities, and refine their teaching strategies. By leveraging Genyo Day effectively, educators create a dynamic learning environment that promotes engagement and academic excellence.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO3: "It was a great avenue for us to pause and catch up with our lacking assessments."

SO4: "If there are lessons that need to be discussed to compensate for delayed lessons, the teacher can use their time to teach during Genyo Day."

SO6: "I can use it for reviewing and advance reading."

TO2: "It's an alternative way to deliver instructions especially when there is no time to discuss anymore through uploading video lecture."

TO4: "Genyo Day helps us catch up on missed classes due to school events."

T13: "Teachers can deliver instructions effectively through uploaded video lectures and shared PowerPoint presentations."

With the emergence of technology in education, elearning plays an important role in the system. Elearning positively impacts learners' learning outcomes, improving critical thinking, regulation, learning ability, and academic achievement (Huang & Sun, 2022). Another study by Mohammadi (2021), elearning helps in increasing student engagement, attendance, and motivation, while challenging traditional learning methods and providing creative and practical ideas. This means that with the aid of LMS such as Genyo, students can increase their motivation and engagement in learning. Likewise, teachers can effectively deliver instructions through various media.

Theme 2: Issues and Challenges in the Implementation of Genyo Day

Genyo Day presents both teachers and students with a unique set of challenges and issues that significantly impact their educational experience. From technical difficulties such as server reliability and slow internet connections to usability concerns like complicated interfaces and forgotten login credentials, these challenges often hinder seamless learning and instructional processes. Students face frustrations with inconsistent access to learning materials and the platform's functionality. Moreover, teachers encounter difficulties in managing and utilizing Genyo Day effectively, ranging from scheduling conflicts to the need for thorough technical support. Addressing these issues requires collaborative efforts to streamline operations, improve technical infrastructure, and enhance user experience, ensuring Genyo Day serves its intended purpose as a productive learning tool for both educators and students alike.

2.1. Technical and Connectivity Issues

Genyo Day presents technical challenges that significantly impact both students' and teachers' ability to engage effectively with online learning. From persistent internet connectivity issues and slow server responses to frequent crashes of the Genyo platform, these technical hurdles disrupt the seamless delivery of educational content. Students often find themselves struggling to access essential resources and complete assignments due to these technical difficulties. Similarly, teachers face frustration when planning and executing lessons, as it compromises their ability to provide a consistent learning experience. These issues highlight the critical need for robust technical support and infrastructure to ensure that Genyo can fulfill its role as a reliable learning management system.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO7: "Poor performance of the online platform in terms of functionality, interactive interface, and speed."

S11: "To be honest, and without offense intended, I prefer NEO LMS over Genyo because my classmates, friends, and I have encountered numerous technical issues with Genyo compared to the previous LMS. Genyo also lacks organization, and its frequent login requirement makes it time-consuming."

S18: "On online, the issues were, there once an error entering the Genyo site which I can't log in, and in error when I click the item or subjects, it log out." TO1: "The connectivity of the internet."

TO4: "Slow internet connection inside the school hinders the full potential of Genyo."

T18: "Technical difficulties such as poor internet connectivity, software glitches, or hardware problems hinder the learning process."

Learning Management System can aid in the teaching and learning process. However, with the technical issues, it can disrupt the delivery of educational content. In the study of Alshammari (2020), technical support, instructional design, and perceived self-efficacy significantly influence students' use of learning management systems, affecting perceived ease of use and usefulness. This suggests that technical support and instructional design should be provided in the use of LMS such as Genyo to aid students in learning. Another study by Flores et.al (2022), highlights that technical problems when downloading study material cause 21.4% of students to not fully agree

with the functionality of the learning management system. This suggests that technical issues must be addressed in using learning management system.

2.2. Misuse and Productivity Concerns

Despite its intended purpose, Genyo Day often deviates from its educational objectives due to administrative decisions and scheduling conflicts. Teachers frequently find themselves navigating in seminars and meetings scheduled on Genyo Day, which disrupts planned lesson schedules and the continuity of learning tasks. This misuse of Genyo Day not only undermines its potential as a dedicated educational platform but also leads to productivity concerns among educators, who may perceive these days as less effective for academic engagement and more as opportunities for non-educational activities.

Some of the verbalizations of the teachers are as follows:

TO5: "Whenever students use it as an escape since they term Genyo day as rest day."

TO8: "Sometimes, students take Genyo day for granted."

T12: "It is supposed to be Genyo day, but sometimes seminars and meetings are held on Genyo day."

T13: "It is not usually used for its intended purpose because most of the time, Genyo Day is being used for seminars and meetings instead of the promised intention that it may be used for checking activities or

quizzes from the previous weeks."

T21: "It is called "GENYO Day" but there is no strict monitoring of classes. Other teachers become unproductive in these days making it as a rest day."

Lower productivity among students and teachers is due to procrastination. Procrastination is a major problem among senior high school students (Tiboron, 2021). It was found out in the study of Alaya (2021) that academic procrastination has a negative impact on academic achievement and performance. This implies that students who took Genyo day as a rest day might create an impact to their learning. In the study of Sun & Kim (2022), online learning environment has been shown to exacerbate procrastination among students compared to face-to-face settings. A study collecting data from 157 college students found that they procrastinated more in online courses than in-person classes. This

means that when students stay in their homes and have an online learning, they tend to procrastinate more.

Theme 3: Recommendations for Improvement of the Implementation of Genyo Day

Both teachers and students highlight key areas where enhancements be done especially in the Genyo app as a learning management system. From technical upgrades aimed at improving server reliability and internet connectivity to simplifying the user interface for better navigation and usability, stakeholders emphasize the importance of optimizing Genyo's functionality. Moreover, establishing clearer management practices, such as structured scheduling for content updates and ensuring Genyo Day is dedicated solely to educational tasks. Suggestions also include incorporating interactive learning features and multimedia content to enhance engagement and foster a more dynamic learning environment. By addressing these recommendations, Genyo day can better serve its educational purpose, providing a more seamless and productive experience for both educators and learners alike.

3.1. Improve Technical Performance and Internet Connectivity

Genyo Day faces challenges related to technical performance and user interface, as highlighted by both students and teachers. Issues such as server reliability, internet connectivity, and processing speed of Genyo significantly impact the platform's usability during critical times like exams or lesson preparations. Students report frustrations with frequent downtimes and slow responsiveness, which hinder their ability to access learning materials and complete assignments efficiently. Meanwhile, teachers emphasize the importance of reliable technical support and the need for improvements in Genyo's features to ensure seamless operation. Addressing these technical hurdles is crucial to enhancing Genyo's reliability and optimizing its functionality as a robust learning management system.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO8: "Optimize the genyo since there are times that the servers are down when we really need it."

S11: "Not all students remember their user ID and password, which can be inconvenient. I wish they could remove this requirement. As far as I remember, NEO LMS does not have this issue; if students forget their ID, they can simply check the student portal."

S20: “Make sure that there is a reliable technical support that will respond on issues during Genyo Day.”

T07: “Improve the Genyo features.”

T13: “Simplify the interface by reducing unnecessary features to make it more user-friendly. Focus on core functionalities that enhance learning and engagement.”

T18: “There must be a stable internet connection during Genyo day for the Basic Education.”

The LMS user interface should be intuitive and easy to navigate for both students and instructors. Poor usability and complex interfaces can hinder effective adoption and usage of the LMS (Juhary, 2023). Studies have found that the usability and user interface design of an LMS can significantly impact its effectiveness and students' satisfaction with the system. Poor usability, navigation, content layout, and interaction design can hinder the overall user experience and learning outcomes (Philip-Balusesa, 2023; Alqurni, 2023). This means that the user interface and overall usability of an LMS have a significant effect on students' effectiveness, satisfaction, learnability, and engagement with the learning management system. Addressing technical issues and optimizing the user experience should be a key priority for improving the performance of an LMS.

3.2. Enhance Educational Engagement

Enhancing educational engagement emerges as a critical focus for Genyo Day, with both students and teachers advocating for richer learning experiences to foster deeper engagement and understanding. Students highlight the importance of multimedia content and interactive features to make learning more dynamic and effective, suggesting that Genyo incorporate these elements to enhance educational engagement. Students also suggest the updating of learning materials in the Genyo. Teachers support this by suggesting virtual exhibitions and educational games that promote active participation and knowledge application. Incorporating these strategies can significantly enhance student motivation and learning outcomes during Genyo Day, creating a more stimulating educational environment.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

SO3: “I recommend that this can also be a day for the teachers to update the learning materials on the portal without having to remind them. There were many instances where learning materials are only uploaded

the day before the quiz despite being asked for even during discussions.”

S16: “Add videos that will enhance user experience.”

T09: “They should have a virtual class to make it interactive with the students.”

T12: “Simplify the interface by reducing unnecessary features to make it more user-friendly. Focus on core functionalities that enhance learning and engagement.”

T16: “To improve the conduct of Genyo Day in Basic Education Department there must be a need of virtual exhibitions- create virtual exhibition where students can showcase their projects and achievements. These include digital portfolios and video presentations and incorporate educational games and activities that promotes learning in a fun and engaging way.”

Integrating collaborative learning tools like discussion forums, group projects, and peer review features in LMS can foster interactive learning experiences. These allow students to actively engage with course content and with each other (Dias & Diniz, 2022). Providing a variety of multimedia content like videos, simulations, and interactive exercises can make the learning experience more engaging and immersive for students within the LMS. This can help cater to different learning styles (Aljader, 2019). By incorporating these interactive elements, the LMS can create a more engaging, collaborative, and personalized learning environment for students, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the platform.

3.3. Implement Effective Management and Scheduling Practices

The management and scheduling of Genyo Day also emerge as critical areas requiring attention to maximize its educational impact. Both students and teachers stress the importance of structured scheduling for content updates and dedicated use of Genyo Day for educational tasks. Students advocate for proactive measures to ensure timely availability of learning materials, minimizing last-minute rushes before quizzes or exams. Teachers propose strategic allocation of Genyo Day to enhance productivity, suggesting it be reserved exclusively for instructional tasks rather than meetings or seminars. Implementing these effective management practices is essential to fostering a conducive learning environment and maximizing the utility of Genyo as an educational tool.

Some of the verbalizations of the students and teachers are as follows:

S03: "I suggest creating a schedule for each subject to upload their learning materials so that students are given the chance to advance read their lessons especially as we heavily depend on the given learning materials as we do not have books per subject."

S19: "I think it is better to remove the genyo day because studying face-to-face is more effective than distance learning."

TO3: "Do not use Wednesday for Genyo Day because some students are not maximizing the use of Genyo during the said day. Instead, make the use of this as an optional by the students."

TO4: "Genyo day should be closely monitored if teachers are really using it during the scheduled day."

T10: "Dedicate Genyo day as a day for teachers to work on papers to check while students are on online mode. Please do not utilize this day solely for meetings and insets so teachers need not bring home their paper works."

Effective management is crucial for the successful implementation and sustainability of school programs such as Genyo Day. With the integration of technology in the curriculum such as the LMS, there is a need to have a thorough study on its implementation. Though, it was proven that e-learning can transform learning from a collaborative approach to a more individualized instructional approach, allowing students to become less dependent on teachers, still, there are challenges in assessing the usability of adaptive e-learning systems (Ritonga et.al, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Genyo Day has provided some benefits to teachers and students, such as academic flexibility, opportunities for rest and personalization, and enhanced learning and preparation. It also presents significant challenges, including technical and connectivity issues and misuse and productivity concerns. By addressing these issues, the school can create a more balanced and effective educational environment that meets the needs of both educators and learners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Basic Education School teachers must upload learning materials early and enhance it to promote independent and interactive learning.
2. Basic Education School teachers must dedicate the 'Genyo Day' to conduct online or asynchronous classes.
3. DIWA Publishing Inc. must enhance the features and functionalities of the Genyo LMS to enhance teaching and learning.
4. Technical support must be given to students in the usage of the Genyo E-learning.
5. School administrators should limit from scheduling seminars and meetings during 'Genyo Day' to allow teachers in doing instructional tasks.
6. Improve the internet connection in faculty rooms to promote productivity during 'Genyo Day'.

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